

RESISTING ENVIRONMENTAL AMNESIA: HBO'S CHERNOBYL AND THE VISUAL RHETORIC OF CLIMATE CRISIS

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Abstract

This paper explains how the HBO miniseries Chernobyl (2019), created by Craig Mazin, not only dramatizes the 1986 nuclear disaster but also uses visual and narrative strategies to create an audio-visual discourse on the contemporary climate crisis and unhealthy energy practices. By depicting radiation as an invisible and slow-moving threat, the miniseries functions as a climate allegory in which institutional denial, delayed action, and human hubris resonate with today's struggles over climate governance. This paper conducts a visual and textual analysis of the series' cinematic semiotics under the theoretical lens of Anat Pick and Guinevere Narraway's Screening Nature: Cinema Beyond the Human (2013), which explores how cinema represents nature and non-human elements beyond anthropocentric perspectives. It also explicates how the series resists environmental amnesia by creating a strong visual rhetoric of an eco-disaster. Key scenes are analysed to demonstrate how the series conveys an ecological catastrophe that mirrors the present climate crisis. To situate these visual strategies within a broader ecocritical framework, the paper draws on Hollywood Chemistry: When Science Met Entertainment edited by Donna J. Nelson, Robert Grazier, Jaime Paglia, and Sidney Perkowitz (2013). Additionally, it draws on Rob Nixon's Slow Violence and the Environmentalism of the Poor (2011) to highlight the similarities between the long-term consequences of the nuclear disaster and the effects of environmental degradation.

By bringing these analytical frameworks together, this paper demonstrates how Chernobyl transcends the conventions of historical docudrama and exemplifies how visual storytelling can illuminate the politics of environmental disaster and climate instability.

Keywords: *Chernobyl (HBO, 2019), Climate allegory, Ecocriticism, climate catastrophe*

Introduction

Climate change refers to the very rapid changes in the temperature, humidity, rainfall, wind patterns and cloudiness which are caused by global warming and human activities. The World Health Organisation (WHO) factsheet on climate change outlines that it poses a severe threat to public health and is the defining issue of the 21st century. (World Health Organisation 2016) HBO's *Chernobyl* (2019), created and written by Craig Mazin and directed by Johan Renck, is a dramatic retelling of the catastrophic nuclear explosion at the Chernobyl nuclear power plant in Ukraine in 1986 and the extensive cleanup efforts that followed. It consists of five episodes with an approximate running time of 60–70 minutes for each episode and is noteworthy for its realistic depictions drawn upon eyewitness accounts of scientists, government officials and ordinary citizens. It stars Jared Harris, Stellan Skarsgård, Emily Watson, and Paul Ritter in the primary roles of Valery Legasov, a Soviet nuclear physicist; Boris Shcherbina, a government official; Ulana Khomyuk, a fictional character representing the many scientists who worked to curb the disaster; and Anatoly Dyatlov, the deputy chief engineer of the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant. *Chernobyl* functions as an allegory for contemporary environmental crises by depicting systemic negligence, misinformation, and human hubris in a visually and emotionally intense narrative. Furthermore, the miniseries challenges the notion of “environmental generational amnesia”, coined by Peter Kahn, a Psychology Professor at the University of Washington, which states the cultural tendency to forget or normalise ecological disasters.

Literature Review

This paper examines the concept of Climate Change, which affects the air one breathes, the food one eats, and the water one drinks, as defined by the World Health Organisation in the Climate Change Factsheet. Its impact can be observed in the rising temperature, leading to increased air pollution, which contributes to deaths from cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. Additionally, it alters the rainfall patterns, which reduces crop yield and results in food shortages, increases the frequency and intensity of heat waves and floods, further damaging the infrastructure, which puts pressure on medical facilities and contaminates water supplies. The World Health Organisation (WHO) fact sheet projects that climate change can cause an additional 250,000 deaths approximately between 2030 and 2050 just from heat stress, undernutrition, malaria and diarrhoea. Hence, WHO stresses the need for implementation of adaptation strategies and strong surveillance systems for climate-sensitive diseases. (World Health Organisation, 2016)

In the humanities, climate change is examined through literature, theatre, and visual media. Hence, the paper relies on the insights of scholars such as Johns-Putra in "Climate Change in Literature and Literary Studies: From Cli-Fi, Climate Change Theatre and Eco poetry to Ecocriticism and Climate Change Criticism" highlight genres like climate fiction and Eco poetry as tools that engage audiences emotionally and ethically in supporting the cause of Climate Change. It also discusses how they represent climate phenomena, along with experimenting with narrative form, temporality, and genres to capture the complexity of climate change. (Johns-Putra, 2016)

Chapters from *Hollywood Chemistry: When Science Met Entertainment*, edited by Nelson, D. J., Grazier, K. R., Paglia, J., & Perkowitz, S., serve as an influential text in understanding the role of media in portraying science and the environment. This is observed in Nisbet and Dudo's chapter "Entertainment Media Portrayals and Their Effects on the Public Understanding of Science," addresses the longstanding concern among scientists that entertainment media frequently portrays science and scientists in a negative light, thereby fostering public animosity. However, the new research suggests that, particularly over the preceding decade, there had been a trend toward more positive, "hero" portrayals of scientists in Hollywood and how Motion pictures make complex scientific and environmental issues more understandable and impactful. The chapter "Narrative Alchemy: From Vision to Visual" by Gambis and "Consonance and Dissonance in Visual Music" by Alves demonstrate how narrative, visuals, and music enhance audience understanding and turn abstract dangers into perceptible experiences. (Nelson, D. J., Grazier, K. R., Paglia, J., & Perkowitz, S., Eds. 2013) (Nisbet & Dudo, 2013) (Gambis, 2013) (Alves, 2012)

Additionally, *Slow Violence and the Environmentalism of the Poor*, Rob Nixon introduces the concept of "slow violence", which is a form of environmental destruction that is gradual, invisible, and dispersed across time and space, caused by climate change, toxic greenhouse gases, radiation, and deforestation. Moreover, works like *Screening Nature: Cinema Beyond the Human*, edited by Anat Pick and Guinevere Narraway, explore how cinema engages with the nonhuman world and challenges anthropocentric modes of viewing. This compilation of essays situates film as a medium capable of altering human-nature relations by showing animals, landscapes, and ecosystems as active agents rather than mere backdrops to human drama. It further states its capacity in evoking ecological awareness among viewers by reshaping perception, attention, and empathy. (Nixon, 2011) (Pick & Narraway, 2013)

Lastly, Peter H. Kahn Jr.'s *Children and Nature: Psychological, Sociocultural, and Evolutionary Investigations* investigates the psychological and developmental dimensions of children's connections to the natural world, introducing the influential concept of "environmental generational amnesia." Kahn argues that as each generation grows up in increasingly degraded environments, people normalise ecological loss, forgetting the richer natural conditions of the past. This process of amnesia leads to a diminished baseline for what is perceived as "normal" nature, thereby weakening motivation for environmental protection. (Kahn, 2002)

This literature review establishes a comprehensive foundation for analyzing HBO's *Chernobyl* as a climate change allegory and resistance against environmental amnesia.

Research Objectives

1. To investigate how HBO's *Chernobyl* functions as a visual and narrative allegory for contemporary environmental crises, particularly climate change
2. To study the role of cinematography and music in shaping public understanding of environmental risk in *Chernobyl*
3. To analyse how the characters in the series realistically represent the spectrum of human roles in the climate crisis
4. To scrutinise the dialogues of the series that exemplify human factors responsible for climate change
5. To understand the concept of environmental amnesia and how *Chernobyl* challenges it

Research Methodology

This paper employs visual and textual analysis to explore how *Chernobyl* serves as both a historical reconstruction and a climate allegory by performing a close reading of the cinematography, sound design and characters' motives and actions.

Findings/Analysis

Visual narrative in films and television refers to how the story is told through the visual medium. It includes the sequence of shots, the symbolic motifs, and the progression of visual themes that drive the narrative forward. The first visual cue used in *Chernobyl* is time, which functions as a narrative device and ecological metaphor. The first episode title, "1.23.45", is based on the exact minute of the explosion. The opening sequence follows Valery Legasov, sitting in his house in Moscow, tape recording his experience in the Chernobyl nuclear power plant, two years after the incident, whilst having his house stalked, he slyly hides the voice tapes before hanging himself at the exact minute of the incident. The narrative then shifts to two years before,

at the exact minute when, from the city of Pripjat (3 km away from Chernobyl), the muted explosion is seen by the audience. *Chernobyl* uses superimposed on-screen text that is layered over the live action to let the audience experience the first few hours of the chaos that followed in the control room of the Chernobyl power plant. This on-screen text drives the audience through all five episodes of the series, from the first few hours in Episode One, to days in Episode Two, months in Episodes Three and Four, signalled through the pregnancy subplot and gradual environmental decay, and years in the final episode. Hence, one observes how by structuring its narrative through the passage of time rather than the spectacle of a single event, *Chernobyl* transforms a moment of explosion into a prolonged meditation on the aftermath. This further elaborates how the effects of radiation exposure build up slowly over time, much like climate change. Initially unnoticeable but eventually fatal. Additionally, this visually enacts the concept of “slow violence” defined by Rob Nixon. (1:23:45, 2019) (Nixon, 2011)

This concept is further exemplified by the eerie blue Cherenkov glow and the flecks of radioactive dust drifting through the air, creating a haunting visual metaphor for contamination. The Cherenkov effect, a real physical phenomenon produced when charged particles move faster than light through water, is here transformed into a symbol of invisible danger, a spectral beauty masking lethal exposure. The show exaggerates this effect to create a visual effect, as in reality, given the circumstances of the incident, its intensity in the air under those extreme conditions would be much dimmer and less visible. Additionally, *Chernobyl* also hyperbolises the medical effects of radiation suffered by the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant workers and emergency responders by showing redness of the cheeks, instant bleeding, burned skin and vomiting blood. According to the United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation, it takes several days or weeks for burns and bleeding caused by high levels of radiation. However, this creative direction foreshadows the biological hazards of radiation and translates the idea of slow violence through visual images. (1:23:45, 2019) (Lanese, 2019) (UNSCEAR)

The Red Forest or the ginger-brown colour of pine trees due to absorption of high levels of ionizing radiation along with the bird falling dead in the streets of Pripjat surrounded by the citizens unaware of the danger and going on with their daily life in the episode one, and the raging forest and the dead doe further visually symbolizes the effects of radiation on the environment and act as a marker for slow violence. (1:23:45, 2019) (Open Wide, O Earth, 2019)

Cinematography, the art and science of motion-picture photography, creates a visual mood and atmosphere by combining technical elements. *Chernobyl*'s cinematographer Jakob Ihre uses colour, light, camera movement, framing and long shots to render radiation, an invisible antagonist perceptible to human eyes. The subdued colour palette of the show is dominated by greys, greens, desaturated yellows and whites, which represent the lifelessness of a contaminated and poisoned landscape, signalling the gradual desaturation of the ecology. Interiors are often dimly lit with cold fluorescent or natural light leaking through narrow windows, which sets a claustrophobic tone for the viewers.

One observes the frequent use of handheld camera work during moments of chaos, such as the firefighters' entry into the reactor zone or the panicked evacuations, which conveys political instability and human confusion, grounding the catastrophe in human experience. The "90 seconds on the roof" sequence in Episode Four was shot in near-real time; the handheld camera captures the frantic movements of the liquidators as they shovel radioactive debris off the roof of Reactor 3. It serves as a sensory metaphor for the slow violence of climate change that operates on invisible, delayed scales. Additionally, the framing of characters also reflects their moral positions within the hierarchy of disaster. Legasov and Khomyuk are often framed in tight close-ups that highlight their internal struggle and isolation, whereas party officials are shot in wide, symmetrical compositions that emphasise institutional dominance and detachment. (1:23:45, 2019) (The Happiness of All Mankind, 2019)

The recurring long static shots of landscapes, especially the forest and surrounding environment and abandoned spaces extend this metaphor of contamination to the non-human realm. These scenes reject anthropocentric storytelling by allowing the camera to grieve silently over the ecological loss. This cinematic articulation of ecological forces is what Anat Pick calls "cinema beyond the human," where nature becomes both subject and victim of human recklessness. The final shot of the abandoned cityscapes of Prip'yat serves as a reminder to the viewers that environmental collapse is both a human and planetary tragedy and highlights the centrality of nature, nonhuman animals, and the material environment to the cinematic medium. (Pick & Narraway, 2013) (Vichnaya Pamyat, 2019)

The music score and the sound design of *Chernobyl* supplement the cinematography of the show as the series composer Hildur Guðnadóttir rejects conventional orchestration in favour of an industrial sound and mechanical resonance recorded within an actual decommissioned nuclear power plant in Lithuania. The absence of a lyrical or consonant musical score and the presence of occasional sonic harmony and disharmony parallel the story's emotional arc and

environmental degradation. Likewise, the use of the metallic groan of pipes, low-frequency vibrations, relentless clicking of the Geiger counter and distant echoes to exhibit the presence of radiation exemplifies Rob Nixon's concept of "slow violence" as slow, invisible decay highlights the invisible advance of the climate crisis. (Fuster, 2019) (Nixon, 2011)

Characters of *Chernobyl* enhance narratives and engage the audience. Scientists in popular media are usually represented through archetypes of the genius, the mad scientist, the reluctant hero, the moral truth-teller, or the bureaucratic victim. Valery Legasov, the nuclear physicist, embodies the modern scientist burdened with knowledge and trapped in government schemes. This is symbolised by his confession tapes, which he records in secret, and which additionally serve as a metaphor for suppressed climate data and silenced voices of whistleblowers. Valery Legasov's journey from loyal bureaucrat to moral whistleblower in the show mirrors the path of contemporary climate scientists who struggle to convey the urgency of the environmental crisis within governmental systems that favour political stability over truth. (Nisbet & Dudo, 2013) (1:23:45, 2019)

In addition to Valery Legasov, Ulana Khomyuk, the composite character inspired by dozens of real scientists who worked to curb the Chernobyl Nuclear disaster, functions as the conscience of the narrative. Her relentless pursuit of accuracy and accountability represents the collective will of environmental activists, researchers, and whistleblowers who resist institutional suppression. Applying Nisbet & Dudo's theory to *Chernobyl* shows how entertainment media humanise science through characters like Valery Legasov and Ulana Khomyuk, who stress the importance of truth, responsibility and the price of silence.

Valery Legasov's voice on the tape in the final episode exemplifies this,

To be a scientist is to be naive. We are so focused on our search for truth; we fail to consider how few actually want us to find it. But it is always there, whether we can see it or not, whether we choose to or not. The truth doesn't care about our needs or wants. It doesn't care about our governments, our ideologies, our religions. It will lie in wait, for all time. And this, at last, is the gift of Chernobyl. Where I once would fear the cost of truth, now I only ask: What is the cost of lies? (Mazin, 2018b, pp. 59)

Moreover, one observes how the firefighters and liquidators embody the working-class victims of state secrecy and negligence, and those who bear the brunt of environmental disasters while understanding the least about their causes.

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Chernobyl communicates much of its moral and political critique through language which is sparse, controlled, and bureaucratic, reflecting the linguistic machinery of a political state that prioritises ideology over truth. The initial denial and arrogance expressed by Anatoly Dyatlov in his response to being informed about the explosion by Perevozchenko is, “You're confused, RBMK reactor cores don't explode. Akimov!” (Mazin, 2018a, pp7) along with his reply in reference to a 3.6 Roentgen/hour reading, "Not great, not terrible" (Mazin, 2018a, pp17), personifies the human hubris responsible for environmental degradation.

Another recurring linguistic motif in *Chernobyl* is secrecy, which is encoded in the bureaucratic dialogue and silence. When Party Secretary Bryukhanov tells his subordinates, “... the Soviet nuclear industry are considered key state secrets, it is important that we ensure this incident has no adverse consequences,” (Mazin 2018a pp 41), he transforms environmental catastrophe into a political secret. As the committee members discuss the possible steps to follow a few hours after the explosion, one observes divided opinions and indecision. This is dissolved by Zharkov, an old, experienced member, who calls attention to secrecy in the following words

True, when the people see the police, they will be scared. But it is my experience that when the people ask questions that are not in their own best interest, they should simply be told to keep their minds on their labour-- and to leave matters of the State to the State. We seal off the city. No one leaves. And cut the phone lines. Contain the spread of misinformation. That is how you keep the people from undermining the fruits of their own labour. (Mazin 2018a, pp 43)

Zharkov's words instil the philosophy of political denial, the same logic that underlines governmental inaction on climate change and suppression of climate data that threatens political of economic agendas. Similar examples emerge when leaders censor scientists, downplay emissions, or discredit climate activism under the guise of preventing panic or economic instability.

However, Legasov's opening words in episode one contradicts this motif of secrecy:

What is the cost of lies? It's not that we'll mistake them for the truth. The real danger is that if we hear enough lies, then we no longer recognise the truth at all. What can we do then? What else is left but to abandon even the hope of truth, and content ourselves instead... with stories. (Mazin 2018a pp1)

In addition to that, his words, “Every lie we tell incurs a debt to the truth. Sooner or later, that debt is paid” (Mazin, 2018b, pp. 54), function as the moral thesis of the series.

The tension between these two linguistic modes, which is concealment and confession, illustrates the larger narrative struggle between environmental amnesia and ecological memory, highlighting the themes of denial, misinformation and secrecy responsible for climate change. Environmental Generational Amnesia (EGA), a concept introduced by psychologist Peter H. Kahn Jr., describes how each generation accepts the degraded environment they grow up with as normal, gradually losing awareness of ecological decline. This leads to a collective amnesia where environmental damage becomes ordinary, repressing efforts to address it. (Kahn, 2002) The TV series *Chernobyl* powerfully challenges this amnesia through its depiction of shifting baseline syndrome, normalisation of degradation, and the erosion of collective memory. Firstly, it shows how ignorance and arrogance lead to conceit among officials before the explosion, as they ignore the leaking valves and malfunctioning meters. Thus, accepting decay as normal. Secondly, it exposes how danger inspires awe and wonder among ignorant citizens who admire the glowing reactor. This reflects how societies disguise destruction with reassuring language. Finally, the miniseries resists forgetting the effects of this nuclear disaster by epitomising Legasov’s confession tapes and the closing historical footage that insist on truth and accountability. (1:23:45 , 2019) (Vichnaya Pamyat, 2019)

Hence, one observes how *Chernobyl* serves as a critique of environmental amnesia by transforming denial and secrecy into acts of remembrance. This historical retelling reminds viewers that ecological disasters are caused by human factors and are inevitable.

Policy Implications

The *Chernobyl* series illustrates the need for timely institutional action, transparency, communication, and early warning mechanisms, which align with the IPCC (2023) Summary for Policymakers. Accordingly, it is to be noted that policymakers should strengthen environmental monitoring and ensure accurate public communication of invisible threats. Equal importance should be given to resisting institutional denial and information suppression. The IPCC calls for governance systems that enforce clear reporting standards and accountability to manage long-term environmental risks. (IPCC, 2023)

Finally, *Chernobyl* shows how narrative and visual media can transform public understanding of environmental disasters. Hence, by combining scientific data with cultural narratives government can educate the common public about the tenets of climate change and ecological degradation.

Conclusion

Hence, to conclude, HBO's historical docudrama *Chernobyl* (2019) serves as a powerful ecological allegory by portraying the nuclear disaster as a metaphor for the slow-moving violence of climate change. The series uses visual and narrative strategies to underline the human causes for environmental collapse. The characters and dialogues serve as moral archetypes of scientists who fight for truth, bureaucrats who deny and citizens caught in the consequences beyond their control

Thus, in representing these human contradictions, *Chernobyl* mirrors the global struggle to understand and address the contemporary climate crisis. Ultimately, *Chernobyl* resists environmental generational amnesia by preserving the memory of the disaster as a warning and highlighting humanity's tendency to forget and repeat its mistakes.

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